

I'm Alberto Hernández, ASC, I have a background of retail experience by six years, took advantage of my work and classes to convert in a professional analyst, also have a bachelor degree in Corporate Finance, as a former Liverpool employee I was able to get into the Liverpool's Quality Committee, and also proposed variety of innovational ideas, all of these focused on improve quality of service and operational profitability.

That being said, I was taking notes of everything relevant I see in my almost a year at Apple Mexico, we are doing a very good job with, high profile training, excellent environment. I noticed some things that I want to expose in this document that may be seen as opportunities or just feedback to grow faster and strengthen our presence in Mexico.

I want to thank you for this events because is an opportunity to see the Apple business in Mexico by the numbers, and that's great for analysis.

The opportunity.

- **Expansion with Liverpool.** They have done all the work for us, market analysis, investment, almost 100 well distributed stores across all the country, 72 of them are Liverpool format which is proficient for Apple business, but the big problem is overprice.

Important data.

-With **12 stores Palacio de Hierro** accounts for **33k** Mac sales forecast for the Q4', *note: they use standardized prices for Apple products.*

-With nearly **100 stores** across the country **Liverpool's** Mac Sales Forecast for Q4' are just **64k Mac sales**, the opportunity comes from this insight *"Liverpool have 9x times more presence in Mexican market by distribution and number of stores but it's sales are just twice of the second retailer of Mac which is Palacio de Hierro"*.

---*The opportunity is to pull Apple price standardization in Liverpool, and cover more stores across the country by staffing Liverpool stores.*

Why we need to staff all the Liverpool Stores ?

If you go to locally and established markets you will find developed and mature markets, metro zones are slowing their grow and soon they will give us one digit numbers, because if one customer doesn't buy a Mac at PH he can just cross the street and get it or compare. Many companies are looking for China, India and LATAM to increase sales, if you go to DF to invest more, you will oversell, in fact we are doing that right now, there's a lot of staffed opportunities to buy an iPad or Mac and *the grow is out DF, out GDL or MTY there in province where we don't sell almost anything because we don't have staff, our opportunity is to have presence in this stores with iMSCs, Flex iMSC or "Multi Store ASC", we can use Liverpool retails for expansion as base for this grow, cities with population over 700k are the key.*

IMPORTANT: *The competition, lately decrease in market share; Samsung is staffing right in those "less important and smaller cities" gaining market share, if you look for market share a year ago in Non-Staffed stores the difference is -35% in other words we used to have a share of 90% now we have 55%, in the other hand where we have iMSC the number is -15%, and with ASCs the number reduces to -10%¹.*

The proof; We have seen that Merida's Region is growing to very good levels, and we need to replicate this success, by staffing more countrywide with iMSCs, iMSC flex, or ASCs that can handle many stores professionally.

¹ Data from keynote, July 11th 2013, ASC Conference 2013.

*****We need more aggressive expansion and cover all the markets countrywide to touch more of the 118M Mexicans with the current ASC program we are covering nearly 26%² of the total mexican population.**

This project is key for future grow of the company, because many stores in province are not going to reach the expected level of sales needed to assign an ASC, iMSC. If we don't take actions our competition will do because *the typical customer think that Samsung is at our level of quality and experience* to compete and yes they are staffing right there.

Thank you.

Sincerely,

Alberto Hernández, ASC.

² Calculated adding the metro population of MEX, GDL, MTY, and cities from Merida's region divided by total population of México as a country.